

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY FROM STUDENTS PERSPECTIVE ON AWARENESS, ATTITUDE AND CHALLENGES TOWARDS ONLINE INVESTMENT PLATFORMS IN ASSAM

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ABSTRACT

Currently, India is the most populated country in the world. With such large number of population, it becomes very difficult for the citizen of India to find a job. So, they need to change their mentality of earning their livelihood along with 9-5 jobs to online investment which could give them a good return, if amount invested after proper market analysis (fundamental and technical analysis). Therefore, this study aims at understanding the attitude, challenges and awareness among the students of Assam towards the online investment platform. An online investment platform is a website or app where the investor can buy, sell and manage investment like stocks, bonds and mutual fund. It allows the investor to make investment decisions and monitor their portfolio from computer or smartphone. Since today's youth or students are considered as the future of Nation, so researchers have collected data from students of different colleges and Universities of Assam. At present date scenario knowledge and awareness about the online investment is very vital.

Keywords: Fundamental Analysis, Technical Analysis, Portfolio, Scenario, Online Investment, Mutual Fund, Stocks, Bonds, Market Analysis.

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2. INTRODUCTION

Investment is one of the most popular form of avenue of earning income. At the age of digitalization and modern era, online investment platforms has played a vital role for generating income avenue among the students community. By making investment through online mode, an individual always try to get higher return with limited resources.

At the edge of modern technological advancements and digitization era, online mode and easy Internet access make it too faster to get information about the investment patterns and avenue. An awareness about the online investment platforms among the students will basically help to identify the potentiality and importance of financial landscape in today's education system. Due to the lack of knowledge of investment education and its related literature, a student always finds it difficult to make online investment. In this research, we will explore the extent of students' awareness of online investment platforms, examine their attitudes towards these platforms, and investigate the specific challenges they encounter. By gathering and analyzing data directly from students, this empirical study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape of online investing among the student population in Assam.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Priyadarshini, (2021), studied on the investor's perception about online trading in Indian Stock market. And the major findings were-
 - a) It was found that 42% of the respondents are the age group of 26-40 years.
 - b) It was found that majority of the respondents are UG.
 - c) It was found that 41.3% of the respondents are private employees.
 - d) It was found that 40% of the respondents' annual income are Rs1 lakh – Rs 2 lakh.
 - e) It was found that 48% of the respondents invest less than Rs 10,000 in online trading.
 - f) It was found that 53.3% of the respondents trade through NSE
 - g) It was found that 25.3% of the investor's brokering site are upstox.
 - h) It was found that 40.7 % of the respondents agreed that their broker is very successful in trading.
2. Dalvi, et al, (2023), studied on the online trading. And the major findings were-
 - a) The investor is able to know the risk and returns of shares by online trading.
 - b) Investors can decide whether they want long term or short term investments.
 - c) Investors must have basic idea or knowledge about computer operations.
 - d) Avoid buying shares of capital of a company having an equity capital of less than Rs. 1 crore.
3. Prasad, et al, (2022), studied on the evaluation of online trading in India. And the problem of online investor identified through this research is that investors are loyal to their traditional brokers; they rely upon the suggestions given by their brokers.
4. Jayanth and Srikanthnaik, (2022), studied on the stock market awareness among college and University students in Ballari. And the study found that Gender, academic discipline, family income, and financial education may all have an impact on students' stock market knowledge. Even among students with some level of awareness, there may be a reluctance to invest in the stock market due to a variety of issues such as lack of understanding, perceived risk, and inadequate financial resources. It may be an effective tool to raise students' understanding and knowledge of the stock market, as well as their confidence in investing. Peers and family members may have a substantial influence on students' investment behaviour and decision-making.
5. Anasuya, (2024), studied on the awareness towards trading and investment among the youth of Mangaluru city. The study found that a large number of respondents have limited awareness of investment and trading activities. 74 percent of the respondents said they learnt about investment through social media. Out of these respondents, 34.5 percent have actively participated in trading and investment activities. Majority of the respondents who showed interest in trading and investment said they have invested in stocks and their opinion about the risk in trading is neutral. They also said they had only 50 percent of the knowledge about investment and trading.

Most of the respondents concurred that educating themselves through various ways helps them gain better knowledge about investment activities and diversifying the portfolio will help in reducing the risk.

6. Ghonasgi and Ghameria, (2021), studied on the awareness of investment among students. And the findings of this research was that the logistic regression results indicate that there is no statistically significant positive association between the use of digital platforms for investment information and higher investment behaviour scores among college students based on the simulated data. The p-value for the coefficient of Investment Behavior Score is greater than 0.05, suggesting no significant relationship.
7. Shiji and Aparna, (2019), studied on investor awareness towards online share trading. This research found that majority of the respondents are aware that online share trading is flexible, enables transparency, provides diversification, professionally managed, return potentially, provides access to stock, high risk as well as high return, capital appreciation in future, safety as well as productive. The respondents are extremely aware that the shares provide tax benefit. Thus it is concluded that the investors are aware about the investments in online share trading.
8. Gupta, et al, (2023), studied on the stock market awareness and participation among the students. According to the study, students understand the fundamentals of the stock market and are actively investing, but some respondents are only aware of the stock market but do not participate in it. Most of the respondents are receiving educational programmes provided by the university.
From the study, we have observed that 48.9% of respondents agree about their investment in large-cap stocks on Equity, while 32 % of them are neutral about their investment in large-cap stocks.
9. Maneko,(2022), studied on investor attitude towards online and offline trading. And this study found that the online trading system is more beneficial to stock exchange, investors, and companies to access the required information and to know the status of stock market in detail at any time. It also helps the investor to take hassle free decisions and also understand the actual position of the listed companies.
10. Susana and Prabhu V, (2020), studied on adoption of online stock trading with special reference to Coimbatore city based on UTAUT Model. And the major findings was that majority of the online trading users are Male (52.5%). Majority of the respondents age was less than 25 (41%) and most of the respondents were post graduate (47.5%)students who traded through the online platforms followed by the private employees. Majority of the respondents had income less than 20,000 and most of them invested less than 10% through the online trading services. Majority of the respondents prefer to trade through the online trading platforms (47.5%) and majority of them involved in a long-term trading (30.5%).

4. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

- a) This study helps to understand student's awareness, attitude, and challenges regarding online investment platforms which is crucial for shaping the financial ecosystem of Assam, as they are the future potential workforce and investors.
- b) The findings of this study will help educational institutions, and financial service providers to understand about the current situation of student awareness and the barriers they face, helping them design better educational courses and platforms.
- c) This study also highlights the financial literacy of students of Assam by understanding their awareness and attitude towards online investment platform
- d) This study can contribute to initiatives aimed at promoting financial independence among students by encouraging early investment habits.

- e) This study helps to investigate student's perceptions of the risks involved in online investments.

5. OBJECTIVE

- a) To understand the perception of students of Assam towards online investment platform.
- b) To identify the most preferred online investment platform.
- c) To identify the challenges faced by the students while using the online investment platform.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A structured questionnaire was developed in order to collect data from the respondent. The questionnaire was designed in Google Forms, ensuring easy accessibility and convenience for respondents as well as for the researchers. A questionnaire is a set of questions designed to gather from the respondent. This study adopts a descriptive research design aimed at understanding students' awareness, attitudes, and challenges toward online investment platforms in Assam.

6.1. POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Students of different Colleges and Universities across Assam comprises the population of this study. There are around 731 colleges and 21 Universities across Assam. So, the sample was selected using a non-probability sampling technique, specifically convenience sampling, as per the accessibility and availability of respondents willing to participate. The sample size consisted of 150 respondent from 17 colleges and 3 Universities of Assam.

7. FINDING AND INTERPRETATION

Graph 1

With regards to awareness of online investment platform, study found that 91.8% respondent are aware about the online investment platform. And out of that 91.9% respondent 53.4% respondent are investing their money through online investment platform.

Graph 2

Among the respondent who were investing on online investment platform, around 57.7% respondent's primary purpose was to gain experience or learn how it works and 34% respondent for potential of higher returns.

Graph 3

Among the respondent involved 63% of the total respondent have rate their knowledge of online investment as beginner, which indicates that more than half of the total students of Assam have just began to experiment on the online investment. This study have also identified that only 5.5% students have rate their knowledge of online investment as advanced.

Graph 4

With regards to the need for more information or education on online investment platform 93.8% respondent feels that there is need for such information or education. And this study have also found that 45% of the respondent prefer to receive such information through online tutorials and around 41.2 respondent through workshop.

Graph 5

With regards to types of information 71.9% of respondents feels that information regarding investment strategies will be helpful for them.

Graph 6

Among the respondent 48.4% respondent's primary concern regarding online investment is their lack of knowledge, 35% respondents concern is regarding risk of loss and 12.1% respondent is regarding security hidden charge.

Graph 7

With regards to the most preferred online investment platform, this study found that 46.6% of the respondent uses Groww, 26.7% respondent uses Upstoxs, 19.9% respondent uses Angel one, 14.4% respondent uses Zerodha, and others.

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. All the information provided by respondent is presumed to be true and factual.
2. The sample may not represent the entire student population of Assam, excluding those without internet access.
3. Limited customisation feature in Google Forms might restrict the details data collection.
4. Without face to face interaction, participants may be less engaged and less motivated to provide detailed response.
5. The analysis might be limited by the statistical tools available within Google Forms.

9. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to understand from student perspective on awareness, attitude and challenges towards online investment platform in Assam. For this the researchers have collected data from students of different educational institutions of Assam i.e Dibrugarh University, Guwahati university, Tezpur University, Jorhat engineering college, Digboi college, DSK college, DSK commerce college, Tinsukia college, Doomdoma college, Makum college, Margherita college, RD junior college, Digboi women's college, Sibasagar commerce college, Sibasagar girls college, CKB commerce college, NERIM commerce college, Darrang college, Tihu college, Krishna Kanta Handiqui state open university. And the study found that 91.8% of the respondent are aware of the online investment and out of 91.8% respondent 53.4% are actually investing online. This study also identified that the primary concern of the respondent were lack of knowledge and risk of loss and the respondent feels that there is need for information or education in this regards which is lacking in current education system. Thus, this study concludes that almost all the students of Assam are aware of online investment but they hesitate to invest due to lack of knowledge, lack of fund, risk of loss etc. And the students who are investing now are just experimenting in order to gain experience and knowledge.

10. SUGGESTION

1. Given that 93.8% of respondents feel the need for more information or education on online investment platforms, educational initiatives should be a priority. Therefore, subjects like Security analysis and portfolio management (SAPM) should be included in the course, which would be very beneficial for the students to gain practical knowledge about online investment.
2. Considering that 46.6% of respondents prefer using Groww and a significant portion also use Upstox, Angel One, and Zerodha, partnerships with these platforms for educational content delivery could be beneficial and this platform would be happy to do so as it would indirectly promote their app.
3. With a majority rating their knowledge as beginner, the content should be easy to understand and as per the requirement of investors. This includes basic concepts of investing, how online investment platforms work, and simple strategies to start with.
4. Given that 57.7% of respondents invest to gain experience, platforms could introduce paper trading account where users can practice investing without using real money. This would help build confidence and practical knowledge. Although some investment platforms have started this initiative but it must be made mandate for all the online investment platform.
5. Online investment competitions can be organised by the educational institutions to engage students and provide practical experience in a fun and competitive setting.

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